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Tolerance Level Difference between State School Students and Religious-Based School Students on Peatlands

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ABSTRACT

The crisis of tolerance in Indonesia is increasing significantly; many frictions between religious communities happened and even made a fight between them. Because of it, harmony and tolerance between religious communities are needed to avoid disunity. The condition of tolerance among religious people in each region is different; the differences level of tolerance in a person can be influenced by their regional origin and education. The purpose of this study was to determine differences in tolerance of students with different educational backgrounds, namely students in public schools and students in faith-based schools. The study was conducted in state-based (SMP) and religion-based (MTS) junior high schools in South Kalimantan Peatlands. Subjects numbered 244 people, with 122 junior high students and 122 religion-based junior high school students. This research is a comparative descriptive study comparing tolerance between students in public schools with students in religious base schools. Based on the results of the independent sample t-test obtained $p = 0.006$ ($p < 0.05$), there is a difference in religious tolerance between students attending public schools and students attending religious-based schools. Based on these results, it is known that junior high school students have a higher tolerance level than religious-based schools students because junior high schools or state schools are heterogeneous so that it is easier to accept differences, whereas religious-based schools are homogeneous more challenging to accept differences because they will assume that all people are the same so they might make conflicts occur and therefore religious tolerance is needed between one another. Besides education, other factors that influence tolerance are found, namely, gender. It is known that women have a higher tolerance attitude than men.

KEYWORDS : Tolerance, Religion-based school, Students

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I. INTRODUCTION

For the last few times recently in Indonesia, there has been a crisis of tolerance, especially tolerance among religious communities. Things that refer to the disintegration of the nation, which is rooted in the depletion of tolerance between religious communities, also occur. During 2018 there were several cases of intolerance that referred to acts of violence. On 7 February 2018, there was a persecution of a monk in Tangerang "The first case of religious violence in 2018 was the persecution of Monk Mulyanto Nurhalim and his followers in Caringin Village, Legok Subdistrict, Tangerang District, Banten, on Wednesday (7/2) and went viral in social media on 9-10 February ". On 19 February 2018, there was an attack on the caretakers of the Islamic boarding school in Lamongan. "The attack on the ulama also happened to a Kiai (Islam religious leader) in Lamongan named Abdul Hakam Mubarak on Sunday (19/2). The victim, who is a caregiver at Pondok Karangasem Paciran Lamongan, was attacked by a man who acted crazy. On 11 February 2018, there was an attack on the church in Yogyakarta. "Cases of religious violence occurred in Yogyakarta. A young man armed with a sword attacked a congregation in the Church of Santa Lidwina, Trihanggo Village, Gamping District, Sleman Regency, Yogyakarta on Sunday (11/2)" (IDN. Times accessed on 19 September 2018).

From some of the cases that have occurred above, it can be seen that the current crisis of tolerance in Indonesia is increasingly alarming, many frictions and even fighting between religious communities. Therefore, harmony and tolerance between religious communities are needed so that we can avoid divisions in social life. Tolerance is an attitude of mutual respect and respect between groups or between individuals in society or other spheres. Tolerance avoids discrimination, even though there are many different groups or communities in a society. Examples of general tolerance include respecting the opinions and/or thoughts of others who are different from us and helping one another for humanity regardless of ethnicity, race, religion or belief.

According to Dany Setyo, et al. (2014) in his journal said that understanding and attitude of religious tolerance of students in public high schools include: tolerance, recognition of differences between people, and with other religions, the difference is as a gift from God Almighty and always respects adherents of other religions to build a peaceful world. Whereas from the results of other studies, it was found that the level of tolerance among religious adherents in

adolescents or students in public high schools was moderate by 83%. The tolerance level among religious people in adolescents or students in the Religion Foundation high school is in the moderate category of 77%. The level of tolerance among religious adherents in adolescents or students in SMA Pondok Pesantren Pati Regency is in the moderate category at 87%. (Cholilurrohman, 2016).

In the context of the interests of the state and nation, religious communion is an important part of national harmony. Based on the results of previous studies, there are differences in the level of tolerance in students with different school backgrounds. This fact makes researchers feel it is important to raise and re-examine the differences in tolerance between students with different educational backgrounds, namely students in public schools and students with faith-based schools. Because basically, religious harmony is a condition of interreligious relations based on tolerance, mutual understanding, mutual respect, respect for equality in the experience of religious teachings and cooperation in social, national and state life in the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on the Pancasila and the Constitution Republic of Indonesia in 1945.

II. METHOD

The study was conducted at state and religious-based schools in the South Kalimantan wetlands by taking students as research subjects. The technique used in sampling is to use random sampling. The subjects of this study were school students on peatlands, namely in Gambut District, Banjar Regency. The design of this study is comparative comparing tolerance between junior high school students attending public schools and MTS students attending religious schools. Data collection for this study was carried out using a questionnaire. The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire with a Likert scale. The questionnaire was made based on Witterman's interpersonal tolerance scale. The scale is arranged based on Allport's theory of tolerance. On the Witterman scale, tolerance is divided into six viz, conformity tolerance, character conditioning tolerance, militant tolerance, passive tolerance, liberalism tolerance, and radicalism tolerance. The product-moment formula is used to test the validity of each statement in the research instrument, while the reliability test uses the Cronbach Alpha formula. The data analysis technique used to test the hypotheses in this study is the t test (independent samples t test).

III.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. MTS Group Data Categorization

Variable	Range Value	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
MTS	$X < 39,384$	Very Low	9	7,4
	$39,384 \leq X < 45,630$	Low	29	23,8
	$45,630 \leq X < 51,844$	Moderate	41	33,6
	$51,844 \leq X < 58,09$	High	37	30,3
	$58,09 \leq X$	Very High	6	4,9
Total			122	100

Table 2. SMP Group Data Categorization

Variable	Range Value	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
SMP	$X < 39,384$	Very Low	12	9,8
	$39,384 \leq X < 45,630$	Low	40	32,8
	$45,630 \leq X < 51,844$	Moderate	48	39,3
	$51,844 \leq X < 58,09$	High	19	15,6
	$58,09 \leq X$	Very High	3	2,5
Total			122	100

Based on the results of the categories in table 2, it can be seen that all subjects in the junior high school group have a very low tolerance level of 12 students (9.8%), low of 40 students (32.8%), while as many as 48 people (39.3%), high as many as 19 people (15.6%), and very high as many as 3 students (2.5%). In the hypothesis test obtained a significance value of $p = 0.006$ ($p < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted, it is known that there are differences in religious tolerance between students attending public schools and students attending religious-based schools. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Safrilisyah (2015) which states that the conditions of tolerance among religious communities in each region are different wherein his research on high school students in Banda Aceh with a subject of 784 students showed a fairly high level of tolerance because Banda Aceh is an area famous for religious areas. However, the difference in the level of tolerance in a person is not only influenced by the area of origin of someone who forms such tolerance, the type of school or education can also provide a difference in the level of tolerance in each person. According to Allport (1954) that one that can influence the level of tolerance in a person is education because education allows one to see the state of society as a whole and view that the prosperity of a group is related to the entire group. So that people who have a good education will have an attitude of mutual respect and respect between other groups or fellow individuals as well.

The types of schools as educational service providers implemented in Indonesia vary, including public and private schools. Public schools are more heterogeneous when viewed from the economic,

social, and religious side, while private schools are more homogeneous when viewed from the economic, social, religious side. In general, people who are used to a homogeneous environment will find it difficult to accept a difference in a society that has diversity. They will assume that all people are the same, and they will tend to sentence something that is not in accordance with what the teacher or parent has taught is wrong. Something is considered true if it is in accordance with what they have learned. Therefore, according to Cholilurrohman (2016), heterogeneous public schools are predicted to be more receptive to differences, in contrast to homogeneous private schools that are predicted to be difficult to accept differences, so conflict is prone to occur, therefore religious tolerance is needed between one another.

In a study conducted by Cholilurrohman (2016), it was found that there were differences in the results of religious tolerance in adolescents or senior high school students. High school students or students in public schools have a moderate tolerance level of 83%. Whereas for students who are in a religion-based school such as in the Religion Foundation High School, the tolerance level data of moderate category is 77%. The level of tolerance among religious adherents in adolescents or students in SMA Pondok Pesantren Pati Regency is in the moderate category at 87%.

While the results of this study indicate that students who attend religious-based schools or MTS have a tolerance level that is categorized as very low as many as 9 students with a percentage of 7.4%, as low as 29 students with a percentage of 23.8%, while as many as 41 students with a percentage 33.6%, high as many as 37 students with a percentage of 30.3%, and very high as many as 6 students with a percentage of 4.9%. At the same time, junior high students have a tolerance level that is categorized as very low as many as 12 students with a percentage of 9.8%, as low as 40 students with a percentage of 32.8%, while as many as 48 students with a percentage of 39.3%, as high as 19 students with a percentage of 15, 6%, and very high as many as 3 students with a percentage of 2.5%. These results indicate that MTS and SMP students in peatland areas have an understanding and tolerance attitude that is quite good so that when they are in the school environment or daily life, students have an attitude of mutual respect and respect between groups or between individuals in the community or within the scope of others, they don't care which group they come from, especially in terms of religion.

In this study, it was found that there were differences in the results of the level of religious tolerance in public school students with religion-based school students in the Peatlands. In students who attend a religion-based school or MTS have a moderate tolerance level of 33.6%. Whereas for state or junior

high school students, the moderate tolerance level was 39.3%. It can be concluded that the number of middle school students who have a moderate tolerance level is greater than MTS students. This is in line with the opinion stated above by Cholilurrohmah (2016), that heterogeneous public schools are more receptive to differences, while students who attend school in homogeneous MTS are more difficult to accept differences because they will assume that all people are the same so very vulnerable to conflict, therefore, religious tolerance is needed between one another.

In addition to education or in this case, the type of school that affects the level of tolerance in a person, there are other factors that also affect the level of tolerance, namely gender differences. This study obtained a significance value of $p = 0.003$ ($p < 0.05$), which means that there are differences in religious tolerance between male students and female students. The existence of differences in tolerance levels based on gender differences is consistent with research conducted by the Center for Education and Culture Data and Statistics of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Education and Culture (PDSPK) in 2017 which found that the sex of respondents participated in contributing to religious tolerance. The results obtained indicate that male respondents have a tendency of 1,171 times to be quite tolerant of activities carried out by other religions compared to combat respondents, assuming other variables are constant. But the results of the study differed from the researchers' findings, where the researchers found that women had a higher tolerance level than men as seen from the mean or average value of the data obtained. In the group of men, the mean shows a number of 46.5417, and in the group of women, a mean of 48.7984 is obtained.

One study that has similar results to the findings of researchers is a study conducted by Arfan & Wahidi (2011) who found that women had a higher tolerance attitude than men where female students showed an attitude of tolerance of 36% while male students amounted to 30 %, so there is a difference of 6% tolerance between women and men. Arfan & Fahmi (2011) revealed that the relationship between sex and tolerance is because, in the view of biology and psychology, it is said that from the physical appearance and attitude of female sex acts are softer and smoother than the male sex. So naturally, women do not like conflict, violence, and the like and are different from men. At the same time, the fragility of tolerance can result in conflict and feud.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion above, it can be concluded that there are differences in religious tolerance between students attending public schools and students attending religious-based schools. The number of middle school students who have a moderate tolerance level is greater than MTS students. This is because heterogeneous public schools are more receptive to differences, while students who attend homogeneous MTS are more difficult to accept differences because they will assume that all people are the same so that conflict is prone to occur; therefore, religious tolerance is needed between one to each other. In addition to education, other factors that affect tolerance are found, namely, gender. It is known that women have a higher tolerance attitude than men.

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VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Arfan, A., & Fahmi, R. Z. (2011). Pengaruh Jenis Kelamin dan Latar Belakang Sekolah Terhadap Toleransi Perbedaan Mazhab Fiqh. *Jurnal Syariah dan Hukum*, 3 (2), 101-113.
- [2] Arfan, A., & Wahidi, A. (2011). Pengaruh Jenis Kelamin dan Latar Belakang Sekolah Terhadap Sikap Toleransi Perbedaan Mazhab Fiqh. *Jurnal eL-QUDWAH*, 1 (5), 183-199.
- [3] Allport, W. (1954). *The Nature of Prejudice*. Boston: The Beacon Press.
- [4] Andersen. (1994). *Multicultural and Intercultural studies. Dalam Teaching Studies Of Society and Environment* (ed. Marsh, C). Sydney : Prentice-Hall, 320.
- [5] Arikunto, Suharsimi. (2002). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [6] Bandow, D. (2010). Tolerance In HR Education. *Journal of Human Resources Education*. 4 (1), 1-13.
- [7] Banks, J. (1993). *Handbook of Research on Multicultural Education*. New York : Mac Millan, 3.
- [8] Cholilurrohmah. M. (2016). *Perbedaan Toleransi antar umat Beragama Padaremaja di Sma Negeri, SMA Yayasan Agama Dan Sma Asrama (Pondok Pesantren) di Kabupaten Pati*. Semarang: Universitas Negeri Semarang.

- [9] **Faridah, I. F. (2013).** Toleransi Antarumat Beragama Masyarakat Perumahan. *Jurnal Komunitas*, 1(5), 14-25.
- [10] **Gorski. (2001).** Handout Pendidikan Multikultural. *Journal of Theaching and Theacher Education*. 1(25),309-31.
- [11] **Hendrastomo, G. (2007).** Nasionalisme Vs Globalisasi Hilangnya Semangat Kebangsaan Dalam Peradaban Modern. *Jurnal Dimensia*, 1 (1).
- [12] **Nisvilyah, L. (2013).** Toleransi Antarumat Beragama dalam Memperkokoh Persatuan dan Kesatuan Bangsa (Studi Kasus Umat Islam dan Kristen Dusun Segaran Kecamatan Dkanggu Kabupaten Mojokerto). *Jurnal Kajian Moral dan Kewarganegaraan*, 2(1), 382-396.
- [13] **Permana. S. D, Noor Rachmat dan Yusuf Ismail. (2014).** Potret Sikap Toleransi Beragama Siswa(Studi Kasus SMA Negeri 5 Jakarta Pusat Kelas XI). *Jurnal Studi Al-Qur'an*, 10 (2).
- [14] **Pratama, Riyan. (2016).** Peran Bushido dalam Membangun Ekosistem Sosial Masyarakat : Studi Kasus Buku Ajar Pendidikan Moral di Jepang (Kokoro No Nooto). Universitas Diponegoro. Semarang.
- [15] Pusat Data dan Statistik Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Sekretariat Jenderal Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan (PDSPK). (2017). Analisis Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Sikap Toleransi di Indonesia. Jakarta: Pusat Data dan Statistik Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, Kemendikbud.
- [16] **Saefulloh, A. (2009).** Membaca Paradigma Pendidikan dalam Bingkai Multikulturalisme. *Jurnal Insania*. 14 (3).
- [17] **Schultz, P.W & Estrada-Hollenbeck, M. (2008).** The Use of Theory in Applied Social Psychology. L. Steg. A.P. Buunk, & T. Rothengatter (Eds.) *Social Pyschology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 28-56.
- [18] **Sugiyono. (2012).** Statistika untuk Penelitian. Bandung: Alfabeta
- [19] **Sukamadinata, Nana Syaodih. (2003).** Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [20] **Walt, J. L. (2014).** Measuring Religious Tolerance in Education. Online. Available at <http://www.driestar-educatief.nl>.
